

Where stone becomes sand and sand becomes stone again – a geological expedition in the Libyan Desert

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The Libyan Desert encompasses four countries, whose population and culture are almost incomprehensible to us, and whose history we know almost only from the “tales of the Arabian Nights”. Our expedition led us to this world to better understand the unique geology of the Libyan Desert, which today determines not only the lives of the plants, animals and human populations living here, as the water and oil hidden in its depths are now an economic factor on a global scale.

Figure 1 Panoramic view of the Libyan Desert (photo: Gáspár Albert)

The geological exploration of the Libyan Desert was carried out by a mixed expedition of Hungarian and Libyan geologists in the autumn and winter of 2008 and in the spring of 2009. We covered an area of about 180 000 km², i.e. almost two Hungarian-sized areas in the Kufra Basin, Libya's most remote desert. The research trip was organised by *Er-Petro Ltd.* on behalf of the Libyan *Industrial Research Center*.

In Tripoli, we were greeted by a pleasant, warm, refreshingly fresh coastal climate on both occasions, which was very welcome after the cold, damp weather in Hungary, and in just a few days freed us from the “city diseases” of Budapest in the autumn-winter months that strained our respiratory tracts. This beneficial effect only intensified when we set off towards the desert. 1,600 km separated us from the largest settlement in the research area, Kufra, which we reached after driving from morning to evening for two days. During the journey, we were able to catch the long-wave broadcasts of the Hungarian Radio in the early morning hours and at dusk (even in the desert), so even though we felt the separation from our usual culture, Home did not seem so far away.

Kufra, with a population of a few tens of thousands, is an oasis inhabited for a very long time. Its ancient district is called Al Jawf, presumably the same as the settlement of “*Dâwd*” in the *Tabula Rogeriana*, an atlas compiled by *Muhammad al-Idrisi*, a 12th-century Andalusian Arab geographer, which predates the Muslim conquest by the *Awlad kingdom*. It was one of the centres of *Awlad Hassan*.

Today, most of Libya, including Kufra and its surroundings, is inhabited by a predominantly Arab population, who are ethnically *Libyan*. They are classified as *Arabs*. This people, who highly value family traditions and community, and who trace their origins to ancient Bedouin nomadic communities, have been living a settled lifestyle since the mid-20th century, but the “tent” as a dwelling is still a national symbol today. The *Kufra Bedouins*, even today, live a semi-nomadic life. In the winter they lead heavily laden caravans of trucks south across the desert, while they spend the hot summers around Kufra. A section of them,

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the " *felahins* ", have settled permanently in the oasis. The largest number of settlers in Kufra are from among them, who are given land near the well fields with government support.

Kufra and its surroundings are the only inhabited areas in this region. In addition, there is only one village with about 500 inhabitants (*Rabyanah oasis*), one military base (*Maatan as-Sarrah*) and a few wells are located in an area two the size of Hungary. The road only leads to Kufra, but the road surface has already become so fragmented from temperature fluctuations that it is better to drive vehicles next to it. With our off-road vehicles, we had to deal with more than just such obstacles. There are military checkpoints on the borders of desert cities, where they check every car. This is an old custom around here. In the past, cities used to defend themselves in this way and thus could earn income from caravans. In most places, they had already been informed about our team in advance, and so our leaders did not have to explain much.

Figure 2 Road to Kufra (photo: Zoltán Lantos)

Kufra is bustling with life, mostly due to its airport and the fact that the Sudanese and Chadian caravan routes meet here. The first time we didn't dare to take part in this life, on the advice of our guides. We didn't even leave the rented house to go sightseeing, where the six of us shared a room of about 25 m² used as a dormitory and office for 6 weeks. The reason for this was that shortly before our arrival there had been riots in the city, which had resulted in several deaths. We were braver the second time. Walking the dusty streets, we noticed a surprisingly large number of hairdressers, internet cafes and small shops, and that teenage black guys addressed foreigners in French. The prices in the small shops were much higher than in the coastal areas, but this was the last time we could spend our money before leaving the populated areas. This time we headed much further south, close to the Sudanese and Chadian borders. The food necessary for camp life – one of the main components of which was live animals – equipment, water and fuel traveled with us in trucks. We had to travel another 400 km on roadless roads at an average speed of 30-40 km/h to the main camp. Of course, we had already started work on the way, as we had to map the geological formations

of the area, which was mostly table-like, with sand dunes and flat-topped rock cones and mountains.

What lies beneath the desert?

The detailed geological exploration of the Kufra Basin began in 1931 under the leadership of the Italian geologist-mapper Ardito Desio (1897-2001), who was a leading figure in Libyan geology between 1926 and 1940. He is also credited with the systematic exploration of the first oil deposits. From then on, oil exploration became the driving force of geological research, but it was not until decades later, in the 1950s, that researchers again reached the Kufra area.

Here, instead of oil, they found “only” water underground, but in such large quantities that serious plans were made to turn the desert into a green field with irrigation water. This abundance of water is found 50-150 m below the surface of the Libyan Desert in old, porous sandstones called the “*Nubian Sandstone Aquifers*”. There are places where water can break through to the surface due to the tilt of the rock layers, and here lakes and oases form in the middle of the hot desert.

A Líbiai-sivatag geológiai vázlatja

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Figure 3 The geological sketch-up of the Libyan Desert

However, the purpose of our research trip was neither oil nor water. For the purpose of basic research, we were going to visit the last 12 missing sheets of the 124-sheet geological map series of Libya. Due to the lack of time, we could only check the preliminary geological interpretations made based on satellite images at key locations. However, there was an advantage to having to visit such a large area in a short time: this allowed us to get a comprehensive picture of the entire region, which made us skilled in distinguishing between sandstones that are very similar to each other, but deposited up to 200 million years apart.

Sandstones have been a feature of this region since the Cambrian period, more than 500 million years ago. Since the first fragmentation of the ancient crystalline rocks of the African Paleozoic, the sand, which has settled and turned to rock, has repeatedly become

recrystallized, uplifted and degraded. The material of the sand layers deposited from time to time has therefore been eroded from the earlier sandstones; the stone has turned to sand and then the sand back to stone, a process that is continuing today.

Our expedition brought new results regarding the last 60-70 million years of the area's development history. We uncovered sediments that are several million years old, which shed light on a previously little-known stage in the development history of the Kufra Basin. The findings allowed the reconstruction of a mostly swampy, but in places river-rich environment of 30-40 million years ago. Groundwater flowing to the surface extracted iron from the highly ferruginous sandstones beneath the marsh, which then accumulated and settled in the marsh. Today, this ancient marsh sediment is present as iron ore on the surface and in places acts as a protective armor for the softer rocks below.

Why and when did this long and peaceful period end? From the end of the Eocene, about 35 million years ago, the eastern edge of the Kufra Basin began to rise due to magma erupting from deep below. The previously flat and humid environment became more rugged. Steep mountain slopes and deep valleys cut into the side of the Ancient Uwaynat Mountain, of which only the roots, the old crystalline rocks, can be seen today. Ring formations, clearly recognizable both from space and on site, are not uncommon in this area. Although they have captured the imagination of many and were thought to be traces of giant meteorite showers, they are actually the heavily eroded roots of former volcanoes.

Man in the desert

Iron, oil and water as raw materials are of interest to Libyan industry. In this remote location, any industrial development would be welcome, but it is also very expensive, so it takes a lot of the raw material to make the infrastructure worthwhile. Strangely enough, it is here in the middle of the desert that most of the water is available, and extraction has been increasing in intensity in and around Kufra since the 1980s.

We didn't always mind the lack of infrastructure. Our nomadic conditions were in some ways more comfortable than the mass accommodation in Kufra, and we could feel the vibrations of the desert both day and night better from our dusty but spacious tents. However, the "romantic" overall picture was greatly spoiled by the noise from the generator and the pollution caused by our presence. Environmental awareness, garbage collection and recycling are unknown concepts in this region, and as the desert becomes an increasingly frequented place, even in these remote places the human presence can be felt through discarded or blown away plastic bottles, cans and car tires. Our hosts only smiled at us as we meticulously collected water bottles and other garbage during our daily journeys.

The desert preserves everything. From Neolithic stone tools to the remains of dead animals to "modern" waste. The latter are unfortunately becoming more and more conspicuous, although the older ones are slowly becoming cult sites and tourist attractions. The wreckage of cars, planes and tanks left behind by explorers of the 1930s and by Italian and French troops during World War II are now popular destinations for tour guides.

The environmental damage affects the oasis itself the most. The city is surrounded on all sides by garbage dumps, and there are already areas in the city that have become uninhabitable due to salinization caused by excessive irrigation. These areas are marked by dead trees, date palms, abandoned houses, and piles of garbage and salt.

Water!

In this dry region, water is a huge treasure. An integral part of the mythology of the people living here is the memory of the once lost "Paradise" that has survived for generations, traces of which can still be found in large numbers in the desert today. These are mostly traces of Neolithic settlements and former river valleys and lakes whose beds are now covered with salt

crust and sand, where trees and other plants still live today, taking advantage of the upwelling of groundwater. They are constantly fighting a battle with drought and sand, and are almost always losing.

The rock paintings discovered on the edge of the nearby Egyptian Gilf Kebir plateau during László Almásy's expedition in 1933 also showed that 10-12 thousand years ago, green fields, groves, lakes and rivers made the environment more hospitable for people. This is the last time the underground "water reservoir" could be filled, and this is also evidenced by the examination of the isotopic composition of the water emerging from the wells. However, there are also much older waters in the same reservoir, but much deeper.

The "Nubian aquifers" form the world's largest underground water reservoir. Its surface area is estimated to be more than 2 million square kilometers. Some of the water fell to the earth in the form of precipitation millions of years ago, well before the emergence of humans, probably during the late Miocene (7-8 million years ago). The stored water represents a volume of about 150,000 km³, which if poured into the Carpathian Basin, would not even the highest peak of the Mátra Mountains, the Kékes-tető (1014 m a.s.l.) be visible from the water. Its exploitation on an industrial scale was first started in Kufra. Here, the goal was indeed to turn the desert into a green field, which was achieved in plantations with a circular layout of 1 km in diameter, automatically irrigated by machines. The fields and farms planted around the drilled wells are geometric spots in the desert that are clearly visible even from space.

The world's largest pipe and irrigation system was conceived in the late 1960s to harness the world's largest underground water resource. This is the "Great Manmade River" or "*GaMRA*". The pipeline began construction in 1984, and by 1996 the mineral water found deep in the desert had reached Tripoli. Today, water does not reach the coast from the Kufra wellfield, but from the oases further north, in the Tazerbo and Sarir oases. The pipeline, the roads, and the wellfield itself are currently under construction near Kufra.

Water is therefore not a scarce commodity in Kufra, and this sometimes gives people a false sense of security. Even a few hundred kilometers from the drilled wells, the desert is still unforgiving. We heard stories of trucks that broke down and were unable to continue, leaving dozens of their passengers dead. That's why we never set off with a car, without a radio or satellite phone, and we always stocked up on enough gasoline in the camp to get us back to the oasis.

Fight for mineral resources

The armed conflicts in the region have made travel south extremely risky in recent decades. Therefore, we were only allowed to move around in the field with military permission and armed escort. Due to the fighting in Darfur, the northwestern province of Sudan, the border has been closed since 2004 and population migration has decreased. Today, caravans can only reach the Central African region via Chad, which is a risky route due to local armed groups.

Political disputes between Libya and Chad, which erupted in 1984 over the transformation of northern Chad into a Libyan sphere of influence, turned this area into a war zone in 1987. Both sides used Toyota SUVs, which are also used for desert transportation, to transport troops, which is why the armed conflict is also known as the "Toyota War". The acquisition of territorial influence in this barren area was important primarily because of the rich uranium deposits in the Tibesti Mountains. The inhabitants of this region are the *Toubuk*, many of whom also participated in the fighting. This people has lived off the "control" of desert caravan routes for more than a millennium and defied Muslim influence until the 18th century. The ancient inhabitants of Central Africa, the *Zaghawa*, are represented in small numbers in Kufra. This people can be traced back to the 7th century, when they established a flourishing kingdom called *Awlad Hassan* roughly in northern Chad, western Niger and

northeastern Sudan. Black Africans arrive in caravans from the south in the hope of a better life, and sometimes spend their entire lives in this "transitional" place.

These peoples preserve their national identity just like we do, and their militancy, fueled by political goals, sometimes leads to conflicts; we have experienced this indirectly.

Pictures

Figure 4 Members of the expedition; standing row from left to right: Miklós Lóránt, János Kalmár, Zsolt Réti, Jalal B. Al Mabrouk, Géza Császár, Kornél Csonotos, Expedition leader Bashir Omar El Mehdi, the camp cook and, on the far right, the author Albert Gáspár; in the bottom row, the expedition drivers (photo: Khalid Trish).

Figure 5 Resting herd of camels (photo: Gáspár Albert).

Figure 6 The Rabyanah Sand Sea (Ramlah Rabyanah) dunes (photo: Gáspár Albert).

Figure 7 In addition to the fuel, water and spare parts that almost completely fill the usual transport capacity in Europe, the payload and passengers looking for casual work will be placed on top of the cargo (photo: Gáspár Albert).

Figure 8 A characteristic formation of the Libyan Desert is the reddish-brown "Nubian" "sandstone" which, when brought to the surface, slowly crumbles back into sand (photo: Gáspár Albert).

Figure 9 Kaolinite sandstone was visible even from space. That's why we visited this place (photo: Gáspár Albert).

Figure 10 Traces of Neolithic settlements and tools are often found in the desert, such as this grinding stone. Findings were deposited in the National Museum of Libya (photo: Khalid Trish).

Figure 11 Turning the desert into a green field can be achieved with the help of irrigation machines and the use of tens of thousands of years of underground water (photo: Gáspár Albert).

Figure 12 The “Great Man-Made River” is being built in the Libyan Desert (photo: Gáspár Albert).

Figure 13 The vegetation binds the sand, but in order not to be buried, it constantly tries to overgrow it, thus these places are marked by hills and mounds overgrown with grass, bushes and sometimes trees that stand out from the environment. The Arabic name for this environment, which indicates a transitional state, is “*nabkha*”. (Photo: Gáspár Albert).

Figure 14 of Kufra, irrigation causes the soil to become saline and the vegetation to die out. These areas are quickly turning into garbage dumps (photo: Gáspár Albert).

Figure 15 In the old city of Tripoli, small shops in covered alleys form the Souk district, a popular tourist destination. One of the oldest mosques, the Jami Gurgi, is also located here. Libyan Arabs sit on its steps (photo: Gáspár Albert).

Figure 16 The military escort assigned to protect the expedition also drove a Toyota pickup (photo: Zoltán Lantos).